

1 **The need for consensus on the effective approach to** 2 **control COVID-19 outbreak**

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16 **Abstract**

17 **Background:** A recent study has discussed ways of China's success in overcoming
18 COVID-19, presenting three concerns that occur in China that should also be
19 addressed by each country, namely regarding emergency response measures; mobilize
20 resources quickly; encourage people to have participated in the actions taken. Among
21 the approaches taken by China, three ways consisting of lockdown; the willingness of
22 people to be patient in obeying the actions taken; distancing; in our view, it is further
23 urged to be the similar consensus adopted by each country as at least the three basic
24 principles that required for in the strategy against the COVID-19 outbreak. Vietnam

25 can be a representative example to discuss, understand and realize the importance of
26 these three basic principles enough to say that it also supports them as the first
27 country to date, to our knowledge, with all sufferers of COVID-19 successfully cured
28 at one time, discussing what essentially has not been analyzed concerning the
29 traditional epidemiological approach known to effectively control the transmission of
30 an outbreak.

31 **Main text:** Vietnam has responded timely by immediately announced the state of
32 national health emergency and implemented a partial quarantine or lockdown policy
33 with initially only a ban on coming from and going out to China, Taiwan, Hong
34 Kong, and Macau and the people in Vietnam, unspeakably, are patient and spread out
35 or distanced. These actions of the Vietnamese seem to have had arguably an impact
36 on all COVID-19 sufferers successfully cured in one time and the absence of new
37 confirmed cases of COVID-19 infection that lasted for some time.

38 **Conclusions:** The recent study who thereafter concludes the need for global
39 coordination in interventions and responses to the outbreak by reflecting lessons from
40 China has demonstrated the implications supporting our view of the need for a
41 consensus similarly by each authority regarding at least the three basic principles that
42 required for to be performed in controlling the outbreak transmission, COVID-19, in
43 the form of the lockdown, patience in facing outbreak situations, and distancing that
44 all of those performed simultaneously.

45 **Keywords:** COVID-19, outbreak, pandemic, transmission, control, Vietnam,
46 lockdown, patience, distancing.

47

48 **Introduction**

49 COVID-19 originated in Wuhan City, Hubei Province of China, is still a threat to
50 people in the world. Many countries take dissimilar ways and policies to stop the
51 spread of this already pandemic (also said as a global epidemic). Until now, deaths
52 from COVID-19 infections have reached more than 100,000 people worldwide
53 accompanied by its rapid increased in numbers and spread throughout the world. Qian
54 et. al. have recapitulated the ways of China and discussed their success thereafter, as
55 the first origin, in fighting against COVID-19 [1]. They raised that there are three
56 concerns as occurring in China that every country similarly also to tackle, which are
57 about the emergency response actions; mobilize resources quickly; encourage people
58 proactively and orderly to participate in measures undertaken. Of various acts taken as
59 analyzed by Qian et. al., in our view, there three ways that required for at least that we
60 argue are fundamentally needed and we encourage to be a consensus similarly
61 performed by every authority in the strategy running to control the outbreak i.e.
62 COVID-19 consisting of the lockdown; the willingness of people to patience to obey
63 the acts taken; the distancing. To further discuss, understand and realize the
64 importance of these three ways performed by China, Vietnam may become the
65 representative instance to discuss relatively the interesting role of these three ways
66 enough to say also supporting them as the first country to date, to our knowledge,
67 with all COVID-19 sufferers successfully cured at one time (16 people were
68 confirmed between 21 January 2020 and 12 February 2020, which then all were
69 recovered including a 73 years old patient and discharged from the hospital on 26
70 February 2020) [2]. Actually, the three ways as the three basic principles to control
71 the transmission of the outbreak, in our knowledge, have been around for centuries [3,
72 4], in discussing to what fundamentally has not been analyzed by Qian et. al.
73 regarding fully historical traditional epidemiological approaches that known

74 effectively control the transmission [1] that have been similarly demonstrated, though
75 seemingly unintentional, in the successful recovery of all those COVID-19 sufferers
76 in Vietnam [5, 6].

77 **Main text**

78 *The first basic principle: no in, no out*

79 The type of lockdown or quarantine expected to control the outbreak [3, 4], from our
80 view here, is a total quarantine or the lockdown that does not allow anyone to come in
81 to or go out of the place of the epidemic. The Vietnamese government seems to
82 understand the fundamental of this concept by declaring it firmly in a single statement
83 only that there has been a national health emergency and revoking Chinese visas
84 including stopping all flights from and to China, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Macau
85 which take effect immediately on 1 February 2020, not too long after the first
86 COVID-19 case was confirmed in the country [5]. Nonetheless, the quarantine or the
87 lockdown action carried out by the Vietnamese government is still partial according
88 to our opinion, which in reality seems to correlate with the emergence of 15 new
89 cases confirmed from 7 March 2020 to 9 March 2020 after quite a long time there
90 were no confirmed infections since 13 February 2020 [2]. The majority of these new
91 cases come from "import" cases, namely those who came into Vietnam from countries
92 that the Vietnamese government did not prohibit at the time, for example, one from
93 Mexico, another from Ireland, and 7 from the UK.

94 *The second basic principle: be patient*

95 The noble of being patient has been displayed by both the government of Vietnam
96 with its acts constancy and consistency and people of Vietnam with their obedience
97 when the government of Vietnam decided to quarantine a number of villages
98 containing peasant areas inhabited by 10 thousand people that related to the COVID-

99 19 outbreak with a period of 20 days [6]. This attitude of patience as learned for
100 centuries [3, 4] in our view seems to have quite an impact to control the outbreak in
101 Vietnam with very few new "local" cases emerging when compared to the "import"
102 cases.

103 *The third basic principle: be spread out or distanced*

104 The Vietnamese Government through the involvement of their army has implemented
105 what has been evident for centuries [3, 4], in our opinion, although not intentionally
106 through an order, that people in the peasant areas that quarantined in the COVID-19
107 outbreak are naturally conditioned to keep staying at their home (also known as
108 physical or social distancing) [6].

109 **Conclusions**

110 The study by Qian et. al. that afterwards concluded about the need for global
111 coordination on interventions and response to outbreaks by reflecting-lessons from
112 China [1], as the first origin, have shown the implication as a reasonable basis
113 implicated to what we encourage to be followed-up to be a consensus similarly by
114 every authority regarding principle similarities at least on the three basic principles
115 that required for to control the transmission of an outbreak, COVID-19, which all
116 done as a whole consists of a total quarantine or the lockdown, patience on adhering
117 the measures taken and be spread out or distanced so as not to be easily affected by
118 outbreaks as in gathered condition. These all three must run together, as ever done
119 during the 1918 influenza pandemic long-ago, which the WHO recently has even in
120 line by explicitly directing each country to carry out all steps to cope with the
121 COVID-19 outbreak by not limited to do either quarantine or social distancing only
122 [7], which exhibited Wuhan city, China, successfully reduced drastically of COVID-
123 19 active cases just recently as the success instance who perform all these three

124 principles [8]. Dissimilarities on basic principles in coping the COVID-19 outbreak in
125 the matter of people distance each other accompanied by no total (including only
126 partial) quarantine or lockdown will lead to "import" cases keep potentially occurred
127 and much more, coming from abroad as Vietnam ever experienced [2, 6]; total
128 quarantine or the lockdown without people being patience to obey the steps taken will
129 result in more "local" transmission and cases happening, as Italy onerously facing [9];
130 total quarantine or the lockdown accompanied by people gathered in the area will lead
131 to the outburst of transmitted cases and even fatalities, as practised-turn out disastrous
132 on the Diamond Princess cruise ship situation as a closed site of COVID-19 outbreak
133 [10].

134

135 **Abbreviations**

136 COVID-19: Coronavirus disease 2019

137 UK: United Kingdom

138 WHO: World Health Organization

139

140 **Declarations**

141 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

142 Not applicable

143 **Consent for publication**

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146 This published article includes all data generated or analyzed during this study.

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148 The authors declare to have no competing interests.

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151 **Author's contributions**

152 FZA and MKS contributed equally to this work. FZA conceptualized the study;
153 analyzed and interpreted all data, and was a major contributor in writing the
154 manuscript. MKS conceptualized the study; analyzed and interpreted all data, and was
155 a major contributor in critically revised the manuscript. ZA inspired the study and
156 critically revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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